

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Supplementary Notes 1: Methodology of $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ Dating

Mineral Separation

The samples were crushed and sieved; material from the 355-500 μm size fraction was separated and cleaned thoroughly in deionized water before drying overnight at 55°C. Magnetic crystals and groundmass such as magnetite, biotite, and amphibole were separated from the non-magnetic minerals (sanidine, plagioclase, and quartz) using a Frantz Isodynamic Magnetic Separator. Lithium Heteropolytungstate (LST) heavy liquid was used to separate sanidine from plagioclase and quartz. Individual sanidine crystals were handpicked from the YTT and Samosir dome samples to select euhedral and unfractured crystals with few to no inclusions. No sanidine crystals were found in the Pardepur dome samples so plagioclase crystals were selected for dating instead. The samples were then leached in 15% hydrofluoric acid (HF) for eight minutes to remove adhered glass before being ultrasonically cleaned in triple distilled water and dried overnight at 55°C. Each sample was sieved again to remove any fine-grained particles produced during the acid leaching process.

$^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ Dating

Sanidine and plagioclase crystals were handpicked under a binocular microscope to a purity of >99.9%. Approximately 20 handpicked crystals (>10 mg) for each sample were packed into aluminum capsules and subsequently vacuum-sealed in quartz vials. Standard crystals of a known age (FCT-NM; Fish Canyon Tuff sanidine standards produced from the New Mexico Geochronology Research Laboratory in Socorro, New Mexico) were packed into copper capsules

and loaded in quartz vials to measure the neutron flux in the reactor to ultimately obtain a J-curve needed for the age calculations. The heights of each packed sample were recorded and determined using vernier calipers before being irradiated. The quartz vials were irradiated at the TRIGA (Cadmium-Lined In-Core Irradiation Tube (CLICIT)-position) nuclear reactor at Oregon State University for 30 minutes (16-OSU-02; 17-OSU-04). After the two-week cool down period, all the capsules were unpacked and the standards (flux monitors) were separated from the samples. Individual crystals for both the flux monitors (FCT-NM) and the samples were individually loaded into copper (Cu) planchettes for analysis on the ARGUS-VI multicollector mass spectrometer outfitted with four Faraday collectors (each outfitted with 10^{12} ohm resistors) and an ion-counting CuBe electron multiplier (CDD), located next to the lowest mass Faraday collector. This set up allows for all argon isotopes (mass 36 on the multiplier; mass 37, 38, 39, 40 on the four Faraday cups) to be measured simultaneously. The Cu-planchettes were then loaded in an ultra-high vacuum sample chamber. Furthermore, the ARGUS-VI can be run in full multi-collector mode, while the highly sensitive electron multiplier measures the lowest mass peak (mass 36). This multiplier has a high peak/noise ratio and low dark/noise ratio.

The flux monitors were analyzed first by the total fusion method on individual crystals to create a J-curve for the age calculation. Individual J-values for each sample were calculated by parabolic extrapolation of the measured flux gradient against the irradiation height and typically give 0.1-0.15% uncertainties (1σ). The unknown samples were analyzed by incrementally heating single crystals of sanidine, while the plagioclase crystals were analyzed using a combination of incrementally heating single crystals and single crystal total fusion. Within the crystal size fraction range of 300 -500 μm , plagioclase crystals on the larger end were analyzed by incremental heating

while crystals on the smaller end were analyzed by single crystal total fusion. Both incremental heating and total fusion of the crystals used a defocused 25 W CO₂ laser beam, scanning across the crystal in preset patterns to heat each sample evenly. After heating, reactive gases within the laser chamber and extraction line were cleaned using a SAES Zr-Al ST101 getter operated at 400°C for 90 seconds then exposed to two SAES Fe-V-Zr ST172 getters for 30 seconds; one getter is operated at 200°C and the other is operated at room temperature.

⁴⁰Ar/³⁹Ar Age Calculation

The ages were calculated using the ArArCALC v2.7.0 software¹ and analyzed against the flux monitors, the Fish Canyon Tuff standard (28.201 ± 0.046 Ma; 2σ ; calibrated to Kuiper *et al.*²). Ages within the ArArCALC software (available from <http://earthref.org/ArArCALC/>) were calculated as both a weighted mean age (with $1/\sigma^2$ weighting factor³) and as a YORK2 least-squares fits (with correlated errors⁴). Ages were calculated using the corrected decay constant $5.530 \pm 0.097 \times 10^{-10} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (at 2σ)^{5,6}. Other constants used in the age calculations can be found in Koppers *et al.*⁷ (Table 2 within). Calculated ages and error estimates include the corrections for blanks, baselines, irradiation production ratios, mass fractionation, and radioactive decay.

Ages measured and calculated include plateau ages, calculated from incremental heating data and total fusion ages (Supplementary Data 2; Supplementary Fig. 1). The “plateau ages” are calculated from two or more contiguous temperature steps with apparent dates that are indistinguishable at the 95% confidence interval and represent $\geq 50\%$ of the total ³⁹Ar_k released⁸. Steps were also selected to minimize Mean Square Weighted Deviates (MSWD) of plateau age to fall within calculated 2σ confidence limit for full external errors. Steps that did not fit onto the

isochron plots, or showed an excess in argon, possibly from micro inclusions, were not included in the age calculations. In the calculation of the plateau ages, Supplementary Data 2 shows selected steps in green, while unselected steps in red, in the “Steps used in age calculation” column. K/Ca ratios for all analyses are calculated weighted on the highest precision, not overall K/Ca values. Isochron analyses were used to assess any trapped non-atmospheric argon in any of the samples⁴; in some cases, isochron analyses were used to confirm the plateau ages for the sample. Total fusion ages (a total gas age) were calculated for each sample by weighting the averages of all the ages of all the gas fractions for each sample; this age is comparable to a conventional K-Ar age. The calculation of the stacked weighted plateau and isochron ages are calculated by each crystal analysis being normalized to the first crystal in the sample (normalized J-value and other conditions for different irradiations) then calculating the weighted mean of the ages with an overlap of 2σ ⁹.

Supplementary Notes 2: Methodology of U-Pb Dating

Zircons found to be in secular equilibrium after initial U-Th disequilibrium analysis were re-analyzed for ^{238}U - ^{206}Pb on the CAMECA ims 1270 ion probe SIMS at UCLA. Analytical conditions (for example, primary current and spot size) were similar to those used for ^{238}U - ^{230}Th analyses detailed in Mucek *et al.*¹⁰. ^{238}U - ^{206}Pb ages were calculated following the approach of Compston *et al.*¹¹. U-Pb relative sensitivities were calibrated using AS3 reference zircon (1099.1 Ma¹²), which was analysed repeatedly throughout the duration of the analytical session. All reported ages were corrected for common Pb and disequilibrium using $D_{\text{Th}/\text{U}}=0.2$; ages >10 Ma used ^{204}Pb correction while ages <10 Ma used ^{207}Pb correction¹³ (Supplementary Data 1). Uranium concentrations were measured using $(\text{UO}^+)/(\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_4^+)$, calibrated to 91500 (81.2 ppm U, 28.61 ppm Th¹⁴) yielding a relative sensitivity factor of 0.12. Th concentration was calculated based on Th^+/U^+ relative sensitivity of 0.666, determined on reference zircon AS3¹⁵.

Supplementary Notes 3: Assessing the Age Difference using Bayesian Inference

The critical basis of our study is the discordance between the $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ and (U-Th)/He ages obtained on the same sample. To assess whether there is a statistically significant difference between these ages we developed and applied a Bayesian analysis for comparing two groups. Our Bayesian analysis is similar to the Bayesian t-test model (also known as BEST model) of Kruschke¹⁶, but was modified so that it considers uncertainties of the measured data and weights each measurement in proportion to its uncertainty following the approach of Gelman *et al.*¹⁷. The Bayesian analysis used in this study utilizes a Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) method to generate a large number of parameter combinations that are permissible within the measured data. These combinations of parameter values are representative of the *posterior distribution*. The advantages of the Bayesian analysis over the traditionally used comparison of weighted means or null hypothesis significance testing t-test can be found in Kruschke¹⁶. The great potential of Bayesian analysis to improve resolution of geochronological data has been recently demonstrated on the example of Fish Canyon tuff and associated units¹⁸, where the authors were able to demonstrate age differences as small as 20 kyrs for volcanic events that happened ~28 Myrs ago.

In a simple Bayesian analysis, the model consists of two parts: (a) a probability model for the data, and (b) prior information about the parameters of the probability model. These parameters are the quantities of interest about which we wish to obtain information. Combining the two parts of the model yields the *posterior* distribution of the unknown parameters, and using simulation, we can obtain their properties.

At a given location, let y_{Ai} and y_{Hi} represent the i th age estimated by $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ and (U-Th)/He methods, respectively. For $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ ages, one might specify, for example,

$$y_{Ai} | \theta_A \sim N(\theta_A, \tau_i), i = 1, \dots, n_A$$

where n_A represents the number of measurements obtained. In words, the expression above says that we assume (or specify) that the measurements have a Normal distribution with an unknown mean θ_A (theta A), the ‘true’ $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ age or the time since cooling through the $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ closure isotherm, and known variances τ_i , which we will estimate using the calculated analytical uncertainties.

The prior distribution specifies our prior knowledge about θ_A . We may well have more precise information about the likely range of values of θ , but a weakly informative prior that restricts θ_A to positive values (i.e., time since cooling cannot be less than zero) is the half-Normal distribution, that is,

$$\theta_A \sim HN(\sigma)$$

We can choose values of σ to be consistent with our knowledge of the volcanism at Toba, for example, the earliest-known volcanic activity in the region.

The probability model is then used to construct the likelihood function, which when combined with the prior distribution yields the posterior distribution of θ_A given the observed data $y_{A1}, y_{A2}, \dots, y_{A_{n_A}}$, which we denote by

$$p(\theta_A / y_{A1}, y_{A2}, \dots, y_{A_{n_A}})$$

The posterior distribution will not have an analytically tractable form, but we can simulate from it to draw inferences about θ_A , such as calculating the mean value of θ_A or, for example, a 95% credible interval.

In the same way as described above, the posterior distribution of θ_H , $p(\theta_H / y_{H1}, y_{H2}, \dots, y_{H_{n_H}})$, can be obtained for (U-Th)/He data.

Consequently, we can obtain the posterior distribution of the *difference* between the ages, $\theta_A - \theta_H$, and answer questions such as what is the probability that θ_A is greater than θ_H , and what is the plausible range of values of the difference (Supplementary Fig. 3).

For computing the Bayesian analysis in this study, Mike Meredith (<http://mikemeredith.net>) developed a code written in R programming language¹⁹ that uses JAGS MCMC library accessible from R via rjags package²⁰. The R-code (rocks_ages_final.R) can be found in Supplementary Notes 4. In our Bayesian model, we treat $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ and (U-Th)/He data as individual point estimates (i.e., ages) with an error term (i.e., 2σ analytical uncertainties). The effect of uncertainties on prediction of posterior mean values is incorporated according to the

approach of Gelman *et al.*¹⁷ applied to the “eight schools” example. Given that we have no existing expectations for variance present, we assigned an uninformative prior expectation on the mean parameters to be a broad normal distribution with no negative values. Accordingly, the standard deviation of the prior on mean was set to 1,000 times the standard deviation of the pooled data. An MCMC method with 100,000 burn-in and 1,000,000 iterations was then used to compute posterior probabilities of means and difference of means for each datasets.

The predicted posterior probabilities are displayed in histograms (Fig. 3 and Supplementary Fig. 2) and summarized in Table 1. The histograms show roughly symmetric distributions and can be characterized by the mean value and 95% highest density interval (HDI). The difference between the means and the 95% HDI was then used to answer the question whether there exists credible difference between the compared $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ and (U-Th)/He age groups. If the difference of the 95% HDI of the difference of means is >0 , one can conclude that there is a credible difference between the groups' means¹⁶.

Supplementary Notes 4: Bayesian Analysis R-Code (rocks_ages_final.R)

```
install.packages("wiqid")

library(jagsUI)

library(wiqid)

# I put the 4 columns of data in "Bayesian T-test 4 JK.xlsx" into a CSV file

# "A_..." = Ar-Ar sanidine
# "U_..." = (U-Th)/He zircon

setwd("D:/r/danisik_bayes")

rocks <- read.csv("LT12-PS3.csv")

summary(rocks)

#  A_Age      A_2sigma      U_Age      U_2sigma
# Min.   : 0.40  Min.   : 1.80  Min.   :62.00  Min.   : 7.400
# 1st Qu.: 71.20  1st Qu.:  6.30  1st Qu.:67.10  1st Qu.:  8.800
# Median : 74.50  Median : 13.90  Median :70.80  Median :  9.500
# Mean   : 76.18  Mean   : 26.92  Mean   :71.17  Mean   :  9.865
# 3rd Qu.: 78.80  3rd Qu.: 35.00  3rd Qu.:73.60  3rd Qu.:10.400
# Max.   :184.30  Max.   :112.70  Max.   :87.30  Max.   :15.100
#
#                NA's :36   NA's :36
```

```

nA <- sum(!is.na(rocks$A_Age))      # number of measures for Ar-Ar
nU <- sum(!is.na(rocks$U_Age)) # number of measures for (U_Th)/He

# A simple model based on "8 schools" but with a single parameter (theta) for age
# The prior is a broad (SD=1000), non-negative distribution.

cat(file="rocks.jags",
    "model{
      # Likelihood
      for(i in 1:n) {
        y[i] ~ dnorm(theta, tau[i])
      }
      # Prior
      theta ~ dnorm(0, 1e-6) T(0, )
    }")

wanted <- "theta"

# Two parameters: Separate analysis for each rock
# -----

jdataA <- with(rocks, list(n = nA, y=A_Age, tau=1/(A_2sigma/2)^2))
str(jdataA)

outA <- jags(jdataA, NULL, wanted, "rocks.jags",

```

```
n.chains=3, n.iter=1e6, n.burnin =1e4)

outA

ageA <- outA$sims.list$theta

jdataU <- with(rocks, list(n = nU, y=U_Age[1:nU], tau=1/(U_2sigma[1:nU]/2)^2))

str(jdataU)

outU <- jags(jdataU, NULL, wanted, "rocks.jags",

  n.chains=3, n.iter=1e6, n.burnin =1e4)

outU

ageU <- outU$sims.list$theta

# Compare the estimates of age

par(mfrow = c(2,1))

plotPost(ageA, xlim=c(60, 80))

plotPost(ageU, xlim=c(60, 80))

par(mfrow = c(1,1))

dif <- ageA - ageU

plotPost(dif, compVal=0)

# According to this model, we can be sure the difference is > 0.

mean(dif > 0)
```

Supplementary Notes 5: Methodology of Thermal History Reconstruction

The thermal history of dated samples was modeled by using the HeFTy program²¹, which allows simultaneous reconstruction of time-temperature paths for multiple thermochronometric systems. In so called inverse modelling approach, a large number of random thermal histories is generated by HeFTy and corresponding thermochronological ages are predicted. The predicted thermochronological ages are then compared to the measured values, and if the agreement between the predicted and the measured values is acceptable or good based on a p-value-based hypothesis test, the thermal histories are deemed permissible by the measured data, in other case the thermal histories are rejected¹⁶. Basic input parameters for HeFTy models may include (but are not limited to) diffusion kinetic parameters for modelled thermochronometric system(s), measured thermochronological ages and their uncertainties, diffusion domain dimensions, and time-temperature constraints that can be defined depending on tested hypothesis and modelling strategy. Input parameters used in this study are detailed in the last paragraph of this Section.

The goal of the modeling was to qualitatively reconstruct permissible thermal histories constrained by the $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ and (U-Th)/He data. Four different models were employed to evaluate different aspects of the thermal history that can be revealed from the available thermochronology datasets:

(i) In the first model, termed “*free run/unconstrained*”, we aimed to explore cooling trajectories that can reproduce the measured ages if no time-temperature constraints are applied to the model. This approach can effectively show the difference between the cooling paths for YTT

sample, characterized by a simple cooling through the argon and helium partial retention zones (PRZ), and the dome samples that require a change in cooling rate during their passage through the argon and helium partial retention zone range (Supplementary Fig. 3a). In this approach no time-temperature constraints were applied between the starting and end points.

(ii) In the second model, termed “*Helium eruption age*” (Supplementary Fig. 3b), we assumed that zircon (U-Th)/He ages record the time of eruption given that magmas cool rapidly during ascent (hours to days²²⁻²⁴). Given that there is no evidence of post-eruption thermal events in the domes the zircon (U-Th)/He thermochronometer with its lower closure temperature is most likely to record this rapid cooling. The aim of this approach was to achieve higher resolution on the thermal trajectories explored in the previous approach (i.e., simple cooling vs stepwise cooling). Accordingly, for each sample we set a constraint to $T = 50^{\circ}\text{C}$ (i.e., well below the range of zircon He PRZ – $160\text{-}260^{\circ}\text{C}$ as calculated based on the adopted diffusion kinetic data for cooling rates of $0.01\text{-}10^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{Ma}^{25}$) at the age constrained by (U-Th)/He age $\pm 1\sigma$ uncertainty.

(iii) In the third model, termed “*resurgent reheating*” (Supplementary Fig. 3c), we aimed to constrain minimum and maximum temperatures the samples could have experienced during post-YTT, pre-eruptive storage and ascent. We assume that our samples cooled below closure temperature of feldspar $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ system at $\sim 75\text{-}74$ ka as they retain $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ age of the YTT event, but did not reach Helium T_c because (i) the post-YTT domes overlie the YTT tuff and lake sediments and therefore must be younger and (ii) their eruption occurred later as recorded by zircon (U-Th)/He thermochronometry. Accordingly, we set a constraint to $T = 200^{\circ}\text{C}$ (i.e., arbitrary value well below the range of sanidine/andesine Ar PRZ – $290\text{-}450^{\circ}\text{C}$ as calculated based on the adopted

diffusion kinetic data for cooling rates of $0.01\text{-}10^\circ\text{C}/\text{Ma}^{26}$) at $\sim 75\text{-}74$ ka. Eruption age of the samples is assumed to be constrained by zircon (U-Th)/He thermochronometry and, accordingly, we set a constraint to $T = 50^\circ\text{C}$ at the age constrained by (U-Th)/He age $\pm 1\sigma$ uncertainty. To constrain the minimum and maximum temperature permissible, we set a wide constraint box at the time several kyrs prior to eruption and the time of eruption (defined by zircon (U-Th)/He ages) for a temperature range between 200°C (i.e., above the closure temperature of zircon (U-Th)/He system) and $550\text{-}600^\circ\text{C}$ (at which sanidine/andesine $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ system would be reset). This setting forces the modelling algorithm to generate time-temperature trajectories with a reheating stage, which takes into account any reheating of the samples by the deeper resurging magma that is the motivating force.

(iv) In the fourth approach, termed “*storage duration*” model, we aimed to constrain maximum duration of the “cold storage” by testing for how long the sample could have stayed at constant temperature prior to eruption. To do so, we ignored the uncertainties of (U-Th)/He ages for simplicity sake and forced the modeling algorithm to search for thermal trajectories that contain sections of thermal stagnation between the YTT event and final eruption. This was done by adding two additional constraints that were tested for different temperatures (Supplementary Fig. 4).

An inverse modeling approach using a Monte-Carlo search method (10,000 search tries) was then applied to find thermal trajectories that could reconcile the pre-defined parameters and constraints. Thermal history modeling results of $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ and (U-Th)/He data are presented in Supplementary Fig. 3. Depending on the modeling strategy, each model was constrained by pre-defined time-temperature constraints (blue dots, lines and rectangles in Supplementary Fig. 3).

Input parameters for all the models were as follows:

Diffusion kinetic parameters for sanidine $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$, andesine $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$, and zircon (U-Th)/He systems were adopted^{25,26} – $E_a = 218.5$ kJ/mol and $D_0 = 11.27$ cm²/s (oligoclase/andesine Fish Canyon Tuff²⁵) were used for plagioclase $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ data from Pardepur sample; $E_a = 220.4$ kJ/mol and $D_0 = 2.78$ cm²/s (sanidine Fish Canyon Tuff²⁵) were used for sanidine $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ data from Samosir samples; $E_a = 169$ kJ/mol and $D_0 = 0.46$ cm²/s (zircon Fish Canyon Tuff²⁶) were used for all (U-Th)/He data. Radii of the spherical diffusion domains were assumed to be 250 μm for $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ system based on the size of the analyzed fraction and 65-83 μm for (U-Th)/He system based on the measured average size of the analyzed zircon crystals. A single spherical diffusion domain was assumed for both thermochronometers, which is likely valid for (U-Th)/He system²⁶ but may not be accurate for $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ system but we do not have any data to support another assumption. The starting point of the t-T path was set as $T = 950^\circ\text{C}$ at $\sim 76 \pm 1$ ka, which is the crystallization age of youngest zircon population found in Toba samples¹⁰ which is dated by U-Th disequilibrium geochronometer ($T_c > 900^\circ\text{C}$) and marks the maximum age of YTT eruption. The end of the t-T path was set to $T = 15^\circ\text{C}$ at 0 Ma according to the present-day annual mean surface temperature. No limit on cooling rate between the t-T constraints was imposed.

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES AND CAPTIONS

Supplementary Figure 1: Stacked $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ Weighted Plateau Ages, Normal Isochron, Inverse Isochron, and K/Ca ratio measurements for all samples: (i) YTT (North), (ii) YTT (South), (iii) Samosir (North), (iv) Samosir (Tuk Tuk), and (v) Pardepur (South). Overview of age calculations for each sample provided in text. All errors are 2σ . For complete ages, errors, and MSWD, see Supplementary Data 2.

(a) Stacked $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ plateau ages; (b) Stacked $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{36}\text{Ar}$ normal isochron ages [selected steps shown in green, rejected steps in blue, calculated normal isochron age for sample in red]; (c) Stacked $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{36}\text{Ar}$ inverse isochron ages [selected steps shown in green, rejected steps in blue, calculated inverse isochron age for sample in red]; (d) Stacked K/Ca measurements.

(a)

(b)

(i)

(ii)

(iii)

(iv)

(v)

(c)

(i)

(ii)

(iii)

(iv)

(v)

(d)

(ii)

(iii)

(iv)

(v)

Supplementary Figure 2: Histograms of samples (a) YTT (North), (b) YTT (South), (c) Samosir (North), (d) Samosir (Tuk Tuk), and (e) Pardepur (South), showing posterior distributions of (i) mean values for $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ ages, (ii) mean values for (U-Th)/He ages, and (iii) difference of the mean values predicted by Bayesian analysis using the Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling method for a MCMC sample size of 1,000,000. Horizontal bars represent 95% High Density Intervals (HDI). Note that the posterior means difference histograms (iii) demonstrate that the 95% HDI of the difference of means falls above zero, and that 100% of the predicted credible values are greater than zero. Therefore, for all three samples we can conclude that the means of $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ and (U-Th)/He datasets are credibly different.

Supplementary Figure 3: Thermal history modelling results computed with HeFTy program²¹ for different modelling approaches as explained in Supplementary Notes 5 – “free run/unconstrained” model (a), “Helium eruption” model (b) and “reheating” model ((c) and their zoomed parts in (d)). The results are displayed in time-temperature diagrams as trajectories (a-c) or inflexion points of thermal maxima (d). For (a) and (b), samples are (i) YTT (South), (ii) Samosir (North) (iii) Samosir (Tuk Tuk), and (iv) Pardepur (South). For (c) and (d), samples are (i) Samosir (North), (ii) Samosir (Tuk Tuk), and (iii) Pardepur (South). Thick black lines are the statistically best fitting trajectories; pink and green curves/dots represent statistically good (GOF>0.5) and acceptable solutions (GOF = 0.05-0.5), respectively. Blue dots, lines and rectangles are time-temperature constraints defined based on available information and modelling strategy (see Supplementary Notes 5 for details). Ages and errors used are 1σ . The model was parameterized by the measured $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ and (U-Th)/He ages, size of spherical diffusion domains based on measured and assumed physical dimensions of dated crystals, and diffusion kinetic parameters of Cassata and Renne²⁶ for feldspar $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ systems and of Reiners *et al.*²⁵ for the zircon (U-Th)/He system. For the table insets: Meas. - Measured age in ka; Mod. - Modeled age in ka; GOF - Goodness of Fit where a good fit corresponds to value 0.5 or higher. Ar PRZ – partial retention zone of Ar in sanidine and andesine; He PRZ – partial retention zone of He in zircon.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Supplementary Figure 4: Explanation of the thermal history modeling strategy employed in “*storage duration*” model approach, which aimed to constrain maximum duration time of pre-eruptive storage (Δt) based on available zircon (U-Th)/He and $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ data and computed by HeFTy software²¹. Pardepur (South) sample was used for this example of modeling as this sample revealed the largest difference between $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ and zircon (U-Th)/He ages.

(a) Time-temperature plot showing results for testing the duration of isothermal holding at 290°C for the Pardepur (South) sample. The range of good fit thermal trajectories (pink curves; i.e., time-temperature paths that can produce measured zircon (U-Th)/He and $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ ages) shows, that this sample could have reached 290°C temperature any time between 74.5 ka and 64.9 ka (denoted by t_{max} and t_{min} , respectively, in the figure) and stayed at this temperature until its eruption at ~61.8 ka recorded by zircon (U-Th)/He age, resulting in $\Delta t_{(290^\circ\text{C})}$ of 9.6 kyrs.

(b) Results for testing the duration of isothermal holding at 370°C for Pardepur (South) sample. The range of good fit thermal trajectories shows that this sample could have reached 370°C temperature any time between 74.5 ka (t_{max} in the figure) and its eruption at ~61.8 ka (t_{min} in the figure), resulting in $\Delta t_{(370^\circ\text{C})}$ of 12.7 kyrs.

The results are displayed in time-temperature (t-T) diagrams as thermal trajectories - pink curves show good fit thermal trajectories (Goodness of Fit ≥ 0.5), thick black curves show best fit thermal trajectories. Blue rectangles are ages of eruption events as t-T constraints defined based on available information (see Supplementary Notes 5 for more details). YTT eruption age is from $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ YTT eruption age^{27,28}. Pardepur (South) eruption age constrained by zircon (U-Th)/He, as seen in Table 1. Ages and errors used for plotting the rectangles are 1σ . Blue rectangles are constraints to force the model to go through isothermal holding at set modeled temperature. Light blue rectangles and lines are constraints set by the eruption age of the sample (Pardepur (South))

at the set isothermal temperature. t_{\max} represents the earliest possible time for the sample to enter thermal stagnation. t_{\min} represents the last possible moment the sample can enter thermal stagnation. For the table insets: Meas. - Measured age in ka; Mod. - Modeled age in ka; GOF - Goodness of Fit where a good fit corresponds to value 0.5 or higher. Ar PRZ – partial retention zone of Ar in sanidine and andesine; He PRZ – partial retention zone of He in zircon.

SUPPLEMENTARY REFERENCES

1. Koppers, A. A. ArArCALC—software for $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ age calculations. *Computers & Geosciences* **28(5)**, 605–619 (2002).
2. Kuiper, K. F., Deino, A., Hilgen, F. J., Krijgsman, W., Renne, P. R., and Wijbrans, J. R. Synchronizing rock clocks of Earth history. *Science* **320(5875)**, 500–504 (2008).
3. Taylor, J. Introduction to error analysis, the study of uncertainties in physical measurements: Mill Valley, California, University Science Books, 327 p. (1997).
4. York, D. Least-squares fitting of a straight line. *Canadian Journal of Physics* **44(5)**, 1079–1086 (1969).
5. Steiger, R., and Jäger, E. Subcommission on geochronology: convention on the use of decay constants in geo- and cosmo-chronology. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* **36(3)**, 359–362 (1977).
6. Min, K., Mundil, R., Renne, P. R., and Ludwig, K. R. A test for systematic errors in $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ geochronology through comparison with U/Pb analysis of a 1.1-Ga rhyolite. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* **64(1)**, 73–98 (2000).
7. Koppers, A. A., Staudigel, H., Pringle, M. S., and Wijbrans, J. R. Shortlived and discontinuous intraplate volcanism in the South Pacific: Hot spots or extensional volcanism? *Geochemistry, Geophysics, Geosystems* **4(10)**, e1089 (2003).
8. Fleck, R. J., Sutter, J. F., and Elliot, D. H. Interpretation of discordant $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ age spectra of Mesozoic tholeiites from Antarctica. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* **41(1)**, 15–32 (1977).

9. Balbas, A. M. Application of Cosmogenic Nuclides and Argon Geochronology to Paleoclimate, Paleomagnetism, and Paleohydrology [Ph.D. thesis]: Oregon State University, 172 p. (2016).
10. Mucek, A. E., Danišik, M., de Silva, S. L., Schmitt, A. K., Pratomo, I., and Coble, M. A. Post-supereruption recovery at Toba Caldera. *Nature Communications* **8**, e15248 (2017).
11. Compston, W., Williams, I. S. & Meyer, C. U-Pb geochronology of zircons from lunar breccia 73217 using a sensitive high mass-resolution ion microprobe. *J. Geophys. Res.* **89**, B525–B534 (1984).
12. Paces, J. B. & Miller, J. D. Precise U-Pb ages of Duluth complex and related mafic intrusions, northeastern Minnesota: geochronological insights to physical, petrogenetic, paleomagnetic, and tectonomagmatic processes associated with the 1.1 Ga midcontinent rift system. *J. Geophys. Res.* **98**, 13997–14013 (1993).
13. Schmitt, A. K., Stockli, D. F., Lindsay, J. M., Robertson, R., Lovera, O. M., and Kislitsyn, R. Episodic growth and homogenization of plutonic roots in arc volcanoes from combined U–Th and (U–Th)/He zircon dating. *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* **295**, 91–103 (2010).
14. Wiedenbeck, M., Alle, P., Corfu, F., Griffin, W. L., Meier, M., Oberli, F. V., von Quadt, A., Roddick, J. C., and Spiegel, W. Three natural zircon standards for U-Th-Pb, Lu-Hf, trace element and REE analyses. *Geostandard. Newslett.* **19**, 1–23 (1995).
15. Schmitt, A. K., Grove, M., Harrison, T. M., Lovera, O., Hulen, J., and Walters, M. The Geysers-Cobb Mountain Magma System, California (Part 1): U-Pb zircon ages of volcanic rocks, conditions of zircon crystallization and magma residence times. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Ac.* **67**, 3423–3442 (2003).

16. Kruschke, J.K. Bayesian estimation supersedes the t test. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General* **142(2)**, 573–603 (2013).
17. Gelman, A., Carlin, J. B., Stern, H. S., Dunson, D. B., Vehtari, A., and Rubin, D.B. Bayesian data analysis: Chapman and Hall/CRC, 675 p. (2013).
18. Morgan, L. E., Johnstone, S. A., Gilmer, A. K., Cosca, M. A., and Thompson, R. A. A supervolcano and its sidekicks: A 100 ka eruptive chronology of the Fish Canyon Tuff and associated units of the La Garita magmatic system, Colorado, USA. *Geology* **47(5)**, 453-456 (2019).
19. R Development Core Team. R: A language and environment for statistical computing. <http://www.R-project.org> (accessed January 2020). (2011).
20. Plummer, M. JAGS: A program for analysis of Bayesian graphical models using Gibbs sampling, *in* Proceedings of the 3rd International Workshop on Distributed Statistical Computing. <http://www.ci.tuwien.ac.at/Conferences/DSC-2003/>. (2003).
21. Ketcham, R.A. Forward and inverse modeling of low-temperature thermochronometry data. *Reviews in Mineralogy and Geochemistry* **58(1)**, 275–314 (2005).
22. Rutherford, M. J, and Hill. P.M. Magma Ascent Rates From Amphibole Breakdown: an Experimental Study Applied to the 1980-1986 Mount St. Helens Eruptions. *Journal of Geophysical Research* **98(B11)**, 19667–85 (2012).
23. Martel, C. Eruption Dynamics Inferred from Microlite Crystallization Experiments: Application to Plinian and Dome-forming Eruptions of Mt. Pelée (Martinique, Lesser Antilles). *Journal of Petrology* **53(4)**, 699–725 (2012).

24. Tepley, F J, de Silva, S.L. and Salas, G. Magma Dynamics and Petrological Evolution Leading to the VEI 5 2000 BP Eruption of El Misti Volcano, Southern Peru. *Journal of Petrology* **54(10)**, 2033–2065 (2013).
25. Reiners, P. W., Spell, T. L., Nicolescu, S., and Zanetti, K. A. Zircon (U-Th)/He thermochronometry: He diffusion and comparisons with $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ dating. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* **68(8)**, 1857–1887 (2004).
26. Cassata, W. S., and Renne, P. R. Systematic variations of argon diffusion in feldspars and implications for thermochronometry. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* **112**, 251–287 (2013).
27. Mark, D. F., Petraglia, M., Smith, V. C., Morgan, L. E., Barfod, D. N., Ellis, B. S., ... and Korisettar, R. A high-precision $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ age for the Young Toba Tuff and dating of ultra-distal tephra: Forcing of Quaternary climate and implications for hominin occupation of India. *Quaternary Geochronology* **21**, 90–103 (2014).
28. Storey, M., Roberts, R. G., and Saidin, M. Astronomically calibrated $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ age for the Toba supereruption and global synchronization of late Quaternary records. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **109(46)**, 18684–18688 (2012).